

APPENDIX

A. Proof of Inner-approximation

Given a base set as in (4.a), the affine approximation aggregation set \mathbb{U}_i^{app} can be expressed as (25.a):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{U}_i^{app} &= \left\{ \mathbf{P}_i^{app} = \sum_{k \in K_i} (\mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff}) \mathbf{P}_i^{base} + \sum_{k \in K_i} (\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff}), \mathbf{P}_i^{base} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ \mathbf{P}_i^{app} = \sum_{k \in K_i} (\mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} \mathbf{P}_i^{base} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff}), \mathbf{P}_i^{base} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (25.a)$$

Considering that $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} \mathbf{P}_i^{base} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} \subseteq \mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff}, \forall k$, we can further obtain $\mathbb{U}_i^{app} = \sum_{k \in K_i} (\mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} \mathbf{P}_i^{base} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff}) \subseteq \bigcup_{k \in K_i} \mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff}$.

Similarly, considering that $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} \subseteq \mathbb{U}_{i,k}, \forall k$ from (7.b), we can obtain $\bigcup_{k \in K_i} \mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} \subseteq \bigcup_{k \in K_i} \mathbb{U}_{i,k} = \mathbb{U}_i^{agg}$.

B. Proof of Containment Constraint Reformulation

Given a base set $\mathbb{U}_i^{base} = \{\mathbf{H}_i^{base, BB} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{BB} \leq \mathbf{h}_i^{base, BB}\}$, the affine approximation set $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff}$ can be expressed as:

$$\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} = \{\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{BB} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB}, \forall \mathbf{H}_i^{base, BB} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{BB} \leq \mathbf{h}_i^{base, BB}\} \quad (26.a)$$

On the other hand, it can be expressed in the form of H-representation of a polytope as follows:

$$\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} = \{\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff, BB}\} \quad (26.b)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff, BB}$ and $\mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff, BB}$ are coefficient matrices.

Combining (26.a) and (26.b), we obtain (26.c) as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} = \mathbf{H}_i^{base, BB} \\ \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} = \mathbf{h}_i^{base, BB} + \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \end{cases} \quad (26.c)$$

According to the Farkas' Lemma [21], the containment relationship $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} \subseteq \mathbb{U}_{i,k}$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A}_{i,k} \geq 0 \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k} \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} = \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{BB} \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k} \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{BB} \end{cases} \quad (26.d)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}$ is the auxiliary variable matrix.

Combining (26.c) and (26.d), we can obtain (17.a)-(17.c).

C. Proof of DRCC Reformulation

We follow the widely used the Bonferroni approximation [18] which set the violation probability ε_m of the constraint at row m to a fixed value as below:

$$\begin{cases} \inf_{f(\mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{BB}) \in \mathcal{D}} \mathbb{P}_{\mathbf{h}_{i,k}} \left\{ \mathbf{A}_{i,k}(m, :)\mathbf{h}_i^{base, BB} + \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{BB}(m, :)\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{BB}(m) \right\} \geq 1 - \varepsilon_m \\ \sum_m \varepsilon_m \leq \varepsilon, \varepsilon_m \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (27.a)$$

Thus, for a row m in $\mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{BB}$ that does not contain an uncertain parameter, (18) is equivalent to:

$$\mathbf{A}_{i,k}(m, :)\mathbf{h}_i^{base, BB} + \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{BB}(m, :)\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{BB}(m), m \in M_d \quad (27.b)$$

For rows containing uncertain parameter in $\mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{BB}$, according to the Theorem in [18], (18) can be expressed equivalently as:

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbf{A}_{i,k}(m, :)\mathbf{h}_i^{base, BB} + \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{BB}(m, :)\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff, BB} \\ &\leq \boldsymbol{\mu}_{i,k}(m) - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i,k}(m) \sqrt{\frac{1 - \varepsilon_m}{\varepsilon_m}}, m \in M_u \end{aligned} \quad (27.c)$$

where $\varepsilon_m = \varepsilon / L_{\dim}$. L_{\dim} is the number of elements contained in M_u . Then, the proof is completed.